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**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE AND DECISION MAKING
BEHAVIOUR OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS - A STUDY**

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE AND DECISION MAKING BEHAVIOUR OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS - A STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Managers carry out decision-making using different processes (Nutt, 1990). For example, some managers are results-oriented and impersonal, relying on facts and figures to make decisions. Other managers are sensitive and responsive to the needs and feelings of others and make decisions cognizant of their impact on people. Still others are planners who rely on careful analysis before making decisions, while others are creative, innovative, and take risks, depending more on intuition than on fact (Mech, 1993). The ABCD of decision-making behaviour: Analytical, Behaviour, Conceptual and Directive are exhibited in individuals at the Decision Making level of institutions and organisations. They play the pivotal role, since their decisions are crucial for the smooth internal and external functioning of the organisation. For educational institutions, Principals are the axle around whom the whole system of the institution functions. But the Decision Making styles and behaviour of Principals of all the institutions is not homogenous. The behaviour is based on various socio-economic factors. That is the reason a study was conducted among the school Principals of Kanniyakumari district. The objectives of the study is to understand the various demographic features of the Principals and consequently to analyse the relationship between the socio-economic factors and Decision Making behaviour of the Principals. The study has adopted statistical tools like Simple Percentage analysis, Coorelation and Chi-Square test to achieve the objectives of the study.

Key words: Decision Making behaviour, Analytical, Behaviour, Conceptual, Directive

INTRODUCTION

Research on managers (formal leaders) in different settings suggests that Leadership style, Decision-making style, and Motivation are the three important factors for managerial effectiveness (Bass, 1990). The manager, a decision maker and the motivator in the field of higher educational institution is "The principal", who is the chief of the institution. This thesis investigates the three important dimensions of principals' behavior: viz., Leadership style, Decision Making style and Motivation Profile. Managerial decision-making style describes the typical way in which the principal solves problems and make decisions. Four functions are used to describe Decision Making behavior: Directive, Analytical, Conceptual and Behavioral; and Motivation profile describes the need for the Motivation: Achievement Motivation, Affiliation Motivation, and Power Motivation.

DECISION STYLE MODELS

The present study is based on the model propounded by Rowe and Mason

Figure 1. DECISION STYLE MODEL (ROWE & MASON 1987)

		Tolerance for Ambiguity	
		Analytical logical abstract	Conceptual systems creative
Idea Orientation	Action Orientation		Leader Proactive
	Task Orientation	Directive focused Results	Behavioral support empathy
			Manager Reactive
			People Orientation

Need for Structure

According to the model, brain dominance refers to an individual’s tendency to think and act according to the characteristics of one side of the brain rather than the other. The technically oriented individual is left-brain dominant-- that is, a logical or analytical person. The right half of the model corresponds with those individuals who reason inductively and who think in broad or spatial terms and are gregarious and right brain dominant (Mech 1993).

The decision style captures three varying factors, as concepts, as follows:

1. The way the individual thinks about the problems;
2. The way the individual communicates with others; and
3. How the individual’s expectations of others materially affect his or her performance (Rowe & Mason, 1987).

The four decision styles were determined to be directive, analytical, conceptual, and behavioral. Rowe and Mason (1987) state that these four styles are the cornerstones of the language of style. They argue that a language of style must provide concepts that can be used to describe one’s mental predispositions to process information and to visualize and think about situations. It should also be able to describe problems facing managers, which they call decision situations, and the environment or context in which the decision is made. Each of these styles has its own characteristics such as level of tolerance for ambiguity, level of communication, level of technical concerns, and so on.

OBJECTIVES

1. To comprehend the demographic profile of the School Principals of Kanniyakumari district, namely gender, age, type of school and administrative experience of the Principals

2. To identify the relationship between the socio-economic profile and Decision Making behaviour of school Principals in Kanyakumari district

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Russell D.Souza (2006) studied on leadership behavior of Principals in high and low performing secondary Schools of Goa in relation to certain relevant variables. The population of the study are all the 358; secondary Schools along with the principals could be constituted as the population for the study during the academic year 2004-2005. Data was collected using Questionnaire.

Soma Banerjee (2013) studied the relationship and impact of Principals' efficacy on school performance, the key managerial skills required to be a successful Principal of schools and the identification of ideal managerial skills to be a successful school principal. The findings of the study reveal a strong relationship between performance of a school and the managerial effectiveness of its principal, where the latter is the driver of the former. Performance of the students in the board results dictates the academic excellence of the school. The managerial efficiency of the principal is also driven by supervisory skills, followed by communication skills and cognitive skills.

Valmarie Rhoden Florida International University (2012) investigated the relationships among secondary school Principals leadership behaviors, school climate, and student achievement in an urban context. The findings of this study, was that leadership variables were Leadership Involvement and Expectation. Surprisingly, Modeling the way leadership variable had a negative relation to both school climate and student achievement.

Maurice Demond Williams (2009) has studied the Principal leadership behaviors with regard school climate, teacher job satisfaction and student achievement. The findings of the study were: There is no significant relationship between Principal leadership behaviors and school climate, There is no significant statistical relationship of principal leadership behaviors and student achievement., There is no significant statistical relationship between principal leadership behavior and teacher job satisfaction.

Per H. Hansson Jon Aarum Andersen (2007) in their study on Swedish Principals' leadership style, Decision Making style and Motivation profile. The questionnaire was explicitly developed to measure the motives according to McClelland's theory and definitions. The AMPI measures the relative strength of the three needs, power, achievement and Affliction: that is, the motivation profiles. The results show that 49% of the Principals have a change centred leadership style, 38% were primarily intuitive when making decisions, and 44% were achievement motivated. No significant gender differences were found.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- The present research is designed to study on the problem, relationship between the socio-economic profile and decision-making behaviour of school Principals in Kanyakumari district
- The researcher used survey method (50% through Drop-off Survey and 50% through Mail survey) which is considered appropriate method of obtaining specific data about the research situation. The surveys allowed researcher to obtain data about the Leadership styles of the School Principals in Kanyakumari District.
- **Simple Percentage Analysis** has been used to analyse the demographic profile of the School Principals of Kanyakumari district.
- **Coorelation and Chi-square tests** have been applied to interpret the relationship between the socio-economic profile and decision-making behaviours of the School Principals

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

Table –1. Age and Gender of School Principals

GENDER OF THE RESPONDENT		
GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
MALE	100	41.67
FEMALE	140	58.33
TOTAL	240	100.00
AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENT		
AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
BELOW 40	10	4.17
41-45	38	15.83
46-50	55	22.92
51-55	65	27.08
56 & ABOVE	72	30.00
TOTAL	240	100.0

Source: Primary data

Table 2 Shows the Teaching experience of the respondent. It show that 33.8% of the respondents were having teaching experience between 26-30 years followed by 24.6 % of respondent who has teaching experience between 21-25 years. More details had been shown in the table below.

Table 2. Teaching Experience of School Principals

TEACHING EXPERIENCE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
LESS THAN 10	9	3.7
BETWEEN 10-15	15	6.2
BETWEEN 16-20	35	14.6
BETWEEN 21-25	59	24.6
BETWEEN 26-30	81	33.8
ABOVE 30	41	17.1
TOTAL	240	100.0

Source: Primary data

Figure 2 Teaching Experience of the respondent

From the above table dealing with the demographic features of the school Principals of the Kanniyakumari district, it can be inferred that 58.33 percent of the school Principals are female, 30 percent of the school Principals are above 56 years of age, 30 percent of the Principals have above 8 years of experience in an administrative position and 26.2 percent are Principals of middle school.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROFILE AND DECISION MAKING STYLE

The relationship between the socio-economic profile and decision-making style is examined through Correlation and Chi Square test.

Table 3. Behavioural decision style*principals age -cross tabulation

	Principals age					Total
	Below 40	41-45	46-50	51-55	56 & above	
Least preferred	9	13	15	29	17	83
Backup	2	4	2	11	2	20
Dominant	1	7	13	12	11	44
Very dominant	7	6	30	33	17	93
Total	19	30	59	85	46	240

Source: Primary data

Table 4. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	10.624	12	.572
Likelihood Ratio	45.240	12	.260
Linear-by-Linear Association	.264	1	.673
N of Valid Cases	240		

Source: Primary data

To confirm the result Chi-Square test conducted at 5% level of significance for the predominant decision style with the Age. The result proved with the ‘p’ value greater than 0.05 , $X^2(12, N = 240) = 11.7, p = .572$, therefore it can be concluded that there is no statistically significant relationship between Behavioral Decision style and age of the respondent at 0.05 significance level.

Table. 5: Correlation of Decision-Making Style of School Principal and their teaching experience

Decision Making behaviour	Teaching experience
Directive	
Pearson Correlation	.062
Sig. (2-tailed)	.558
N	240
Analytical	
Pearson Correlation	.054
Sig. (2-tailed)	.412
N	240
Conceptual	
Pearson Correlation	.162
Sig. (2-tailed)	.061
N	240
Behavioral	
Pearson Correlation	.031
Sig. (2-tailed)	.641
N	240

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Decision Making Style has no statistically significant relationship with the teaching experience of the respondent at 0.05 significance level). For Directive Decision style ($r=0.062, p=0.558$), it means insignificant relationship with positive correlation, for Analytical decision style ($r=0.054, p=0.412$), it means insignificant relationship with positive correlation, for Conceptual decision style ($r=0.162, p=0.061$), it means insignificant relationship with positive correlation, and for Behavioral Decision style ($r=.031, p=.641$) shows statistically no significant relationship with positive correlation.

The result reveals that increase or decrease in teaching experience has no relationship with the Decision-making style of the principal. The chi-square result proves it at 5% significance level. All the ‘p’ value is less than 0.05 level of significance. The cluster bar chart below illustrates the insignificant relationship between the predominant decision style and the teaching experience of school principals in Kanyakumari District.

Figure. 3 : Cluster Bar chart for Behavioral Decision style and Teaching experience of the respondent

Bar chart shows that, the principal who have more than 26 years of experience has scored for both Very Dominant and Least preferred level of intensity for this style.

CONCLUSION

The study has revealed a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between certain factors and the Decision Making behavior of the school Principals. Decision Making is a tool which takes into account various internal and external factors into consideration and the best alternative is being considered finally. There can never be the best or worst decision. Decisions not always reflect the age, experience, gender or any other socio or economic factors. Teaching experirnce does not influence Decision making. Technology or some other factors may contribute in today's Decision Making scenario. Research in this area will help in finding the factor that influence effective decision making.

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